

Highlights (for review)

- Two rainfall events accounted for 99 % of total soil loss in the agricultural field
- Soil erosion is an important mechanism of green manure decomposition in hilly fields
- Green manure decomposed three-times faster at depositional than at eroding and transport sites
- Factors controlling litter decomposition varied at different landform positions
- Green manure incorporation is an efficient tool to recover SOC losses by land-use

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4 **Title:** Litter decomposition rates of green manure as affected by soil erosion, transport
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6 and deposition processes, and the implications for the soil carbon balance of a rainfed
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8 olive grove under a dry Mediterranean climate.
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4 **Litter decomposition rates of green manure as affected by soil erosion, transport**
5 **and deposition processes, and the implications for the soil carbon balance of a**
6 **rainfed olive grove under a dry Mediterranean climate.**
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23 **Abstract**
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28 Soil erosion by water promotes the distribution of soil organic carbon (SOC) and
29 nutrients within the landscape. Moreover, soil redistribution may have a large impact on
30 litter decomposition dynamics. There is a current lack of information about the role of
31 soil erosion in the SOC balance of sloping agricultural fields because its magnitude and
32 direction depend on the dominant horizontal and vertical C fluxes at the different
33 landform (eroding, transport and depositional) positions within the hillslope. Therefore,
34 the significance of these lateral fluxes in the local C balance has to be assessed when
35 interactions with vertical C fluxes (e.g., litter decay) are also taken into account. An
36 experiment was designed to increase our understanding of the role of different phases of
37 the soil erosion process in litter decomposition dynamics and the resulting impact on the
38 soil C balance of a rain-fed olive grove under a dry Mediterranean climate, in which two
39 or three high intensity-low frequency rainfall events are responsible for the majority of
40 the annual soil erosion. To accomplish this, four replicate plots were installed at three
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4 different landform positions, according to erosion criteria (eroding, transport and
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6 depositional sites), and two litter types (*Avena sativa* L. or *Vicia sativa* L.) with
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8 contrasting initial litter chemistry (high C:N, low C:N) were deployed in the middle of
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10 the summer season, before the expected occurrence of rainfall events in the experimental
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12 area. Two successive rainfall events led to pronounced patterns of erosion and associated
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14 processes of soil transport and deposition, accounting for 99 % of total soil loss in the
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16 experimental area and leading to the burial of most of the litterbags located at the
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18 depositional positions. The results indicate that soil erosion (lateral movement and soil
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20 mixing) may be an important mechanism of litter decomposition, as litter mass loss rates
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22 were related closely to the amount of soil infiltrated/deposited within the litterbags for
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24 both litter types, decay rates at depositional sites being about three-fold higher than at
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26 eroding and transport sites. Our results also indicate that soil mobilisation by erosion has
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28 significant impacts on C dynamics, causing lateral and vertical fluxes of C similar in
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30 magnitude to those induced by changes in land use or management. According to our
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32 estimates, soil C losses driven by land-use change could be compensated after 20 years of
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34 green manure incorporation in this rainfed Mediterranean olive grove.
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46 **Key words:** soil erosion, high-intensity rainfall event, litter decomposition, soil carbon
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48 balance, Mediterranean agroecosystem, green manure.
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55 INTRODUCTION 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

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4 Soils are the largest carbon (C) reservoir of the terrestrial C budget (Batjes and
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6 Sombroek, 1997). Therefore, even a relatively small increase or decrease in soil C
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8 content due to changes in land use or management practices may result in a significant
9
10 net exchange of C between the soil reservoir and the atmosphere (Houghton, 2003).
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12 Under natural conditions, soil systems are considered to be in equilibrium, as losses
13
14 through erosion and decomposition of litter and soil organic matter are compensated by
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16 inputs from aboveground and belowground net primary production on both short- and
17
18 long-term scales (Giardina and Ryan, 2002). However, conversion from native to
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20 agricultural ecosystems has increased C losses to the atmosphere without enhancing C
21
22 inputs into soil, and therefore the global C cycle has been drastically altered (DeFries et
23
24 al. 1999; IPCC, 2007). These C losses, given by previous native vegetation and
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26 subsequent annual crop removal, tillage operations and enhancement of soil erosion rates
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28 (Lal, 2003; Quinton et al. 2010; Van Oost et al. 2005; 2012), may be compensated by
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30 sustainable land management (SLM) practices. In this regard, the incorporation of cover
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32 crops such as leguminous species (i.e., green manure) into the soil of a given cropping
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34 system is considered a promising sustainable management practice to reduce soil erosion
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36 risk (Almagro et al. 2013a; Alliaume et al. 2013; De Baets et al. 2011; Francia-Martínez
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38 et al. 2006; Gómez et al. 2009) while compensating soil C losses derived from land-use
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40 change and tillage in agricultural fields (Gómez-Muñoz et al. 2014; Lal, 2013; Milgroom
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42 et al. 2007; Ramos et al. 2010). This is an important issue in Southern Spain, where
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44 subsidy policies have induced the expansion and intensification of olive and almond
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46 orchards in hilly environments while overlooking erosion-derived problems, and
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4 furthermore, an increase in the area suitable for olive production is expected with climate
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6 warming (García-Ruiz, 2010; Olesen and Bindi, 2002).
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9 Soil erosion (detachment, transport and deposition) affects not only the distribution of
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11 sediments and associated C within the hillslope (Ritchie and McCarty, 2003; Nadeu et al.
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13 2012; Zhang et al. 2006) but also litter decomposition dynamics through several abiotic
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15 and biotic mechanisms (Barnes et al. 2012; Berhe, 2012; Hewins et al. 2012; Lee et al.
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17 2014; Throop and Archer, 2008). There are several mechanisms involved in litter
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19 decomposition during the process of soil erosion by water along hillslopes. During
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21 detachment and transport, soil deposition onto litter (or burial of litter) may not occur but
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23 collision with soil particles may be an important mechanism driving litter fragmentation,
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25 increasing the surface area available for microbial decomposers transported within the
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27 sediments (Barnes et al. 2012; Berhe, 2012; Throop and Archer, 2008). During
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29 deposition, besides physical fragmentation by soil abrasion, burial of litter may accelerate
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31 decay rates by promoting soil-litter mixing and improving soil moisture and temperature
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33 conditions for microbial decomposition (microclimate buffering) (Barnes et al, 2012;
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35 Throop and Archer, 2008; Whitford, 2002). Therefore, to understand erosional effects on
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37 litter decomposition dynamics the consideration of all three phases (soil erosion, transport
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39 and deposition) is necessary.
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48 As a result of ongoing global climate change, and the increasingly acknowledged
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50 importance of the role of abiotic factors in comparison to biotic factors in litter
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52 decomposition dynamics in dry ecosystems (King et al. 2012; Throop and Archer, 2008),
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54 much effort is being devoted to improving our understanding of the abiotic factors
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56 driving litter decomposition dynamics and subsequent soil C storage. Although the
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4 importance of photodegradation as an abiotic mechanism in litter decomposition has been
5 highlighted recently (Austin and Vivanco, 2006), accounting for the liberation of 1- 4 g C
6 m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Brandt et al. 2009), the role of soil erosion has been overlooked in litter
7 decomposition studies. Most of these studies have been conducted on flat landscapes and
8 little is known about how litter decomposition rates vary along dynamic hillslope
9 environments experiencing lateral soil distribution with soil erosion, despite the fact that
10 these hilly environments account for more than 60 % of the terrestrial Earth surface
11 (Staub and Rosenzweig, 1992). Although recent studies have shown that soil erosion can
12 be a significant driver of litter decomposition in arid, semiarid and Mediterranean
13 ecosystems (Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2012; Berhe, 2012; Hewins et al. 2012;
14 Throop and Archer, 2007), the magnitude, direction and mechanisms (physical
15 fragmentation or microbial decomposition facilitation) behind litter decomposition by soil
16 water erosion remain largely unexplored. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first
17 study to examine the roles of the different phases of soil erosion in litter decomposition
18 rates (but see Berhe, 2012) and their implications for the soil organic carbon (SOC)
19 balance along a dynamic hilly Mediterranean agroecosystem.
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43 The main purpose of this study was to assess whether the process of soil erosion plays a
44 significant role in the soil C balance of this dry Mediterranean agroecosystem, when its
45 interaction with litter decomposition dynamics is considered. More specifically, the
46 objectives were: (1) to understand the role of the different phases (erosion, transport and
47 deposition) of soil erosion in the short-term litter decomposition dynamics of two
48 contrasting species, common oat (*Avena sativa* L.) and vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.); (2) to
49 identify the factors controlling litter decomposition rates during the different phases of
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4 the soil erosion process; and (3) to assess the contribution of green manure incorporation
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6 to the soil C balance of a rainfed olive grove under dry Mediterranean climate in
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8 Southeast Spain. We hypothesised that soil erosion is an important driver of litter
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10 decomposition and that, therefore, litter decomposition would increase along the hillslope
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12 driven by a complex interplay of different factors across landform positions. We also
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14 hypothesised that green manure incorporation would account for a significant C gain
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16 within the soil C balance of this rainfed olive grove, significantly improving its
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18 belowground C sequestration capacity.
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24 For the purposes of our study, we define erosional effects on litter decomposition
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26 dynamics as the direct effect of physical fragmentation by soil abrasion during the
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28 detachment and transport of soil particles and any indirect effect derived from the
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30 breakdown and burial of litter (such as an increase in litter surface availability, soil-litter
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32 mixing and microclimate buffering) that facilitates microbial decomposition.
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38 MATERIALS AND METHODS

39 1. Study area

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42 This study was conducted in an agricultural field situated in Cehegín in the Northwest of
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44 the province of Murcia, in Southeast Spain (38° 3' N, 1° 46' W). It was carried out in a
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46 100-yr-old organic rainfed olive grove without terraces, which was regularly ploughed
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48 along the contour lines and planted with a 10 x 10 m spacing (107 olive trees ha⁻¹). The
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50 olive grove (170 m long by 70 m wide) is located on a convex-concave hillslope facing
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52 Southeast, with a mean slope of 10-12%, altitudes ranging from 600 to 650 m.a.s.l., good
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54 drainage and a high percentage of stones on the surface. The spatial configuration of the
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4 ridges, perpendicular to the slope, allowed the delineation of a set of elongated sections
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6 along the slope, in which the different phases of the soil water erosion process (erosion,
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8 transport and deposition) can be observed.
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11 The climate is dry sub-humid Mediterranean, with a mean annual precipitation ranging
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13 from 300 to 400 mm and mean annual temperature from 15 to 16 °C (Cehegín
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15 Meteorological Station, 1953-1986 period). The mean monthly rainfall ranges from 8 mm
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17 (July) to 50 mm (October), following a bimodal distribution with two rainy seasons
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19 (autumn and spring) and a dry period in summer. However, high rainfall variability
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21 between and within years is very common in the study area, and high-intensity low-
22
23 frequency rainfall events may occur during the summer season, being responsible for the
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25 main part of the annual soil erosion in the olive grove (Martínez-Mena et al. 2012).
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27 Monthly temperatures oscillate from 0 °C or below 0 °C (December and January) to 40 °C
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29 (July and August). The mean annual potential evapotranspiration (calculated by the
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31 Thornthwaite method; Thornthwaite, 1948) reaches 800 mm yr⁻¹, so the annual water
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33 deficit is 430 mm. July and August are the driest months, when the maxima of the
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35 monthly temperature and potential evapotranspiration occur.
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43 The soil in the study site has a loamy texture, is derived from limestone colluvia and is
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45 classified as Hypercalcic Calcisol, according to soil taxonomy (FAO, 2006). Overall, the
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47 soil in the study site is shallow, with an underlying caliche layer at 17-19 cm depth, and
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49 has a low organic matter content and high percentage of carbonates (Martínez-Mena et al.
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51 2008). The rate of soil erosion was measured previously using two closed erosion plots (8
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53 m long × 2 m wide) and was approximately 100 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ (equivalent to 1 ton ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹),
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4 the corresponding SOC erosion being around $5 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (equivalent to $0.05 \text{ tons ha}^{-1}$
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7 yr^{-1}) (Martínez-Mena et al. 2008).
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9 Two moderate to high-intensity rainfall events (maximum intensity in 30 min of 23 and
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11 20 mm h^{-1}) of 20 and 45 mm occurred in the field on 13th and 19th August 2010. These
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13 two successive rainstorms led to the erosion of a significant amount of soil material,
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15 eroded mainly by rill and inter-rill erosion from the hillslope. It can be assumed that all
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17 the eroded soil within each section was trapped behind the furrows, as these ridges
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19 remained entirely intact after the rainstorm.
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23 2. Experimental design and field measurements

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25 As the primary purpose of this experiment was to assess the short-term effects of soil
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27 water erosion on litter decomposition rates, litterbags were deployed in the middle of the
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29 dry season, before the time when high-intensity low-frequency rainfall events and
30
31 associated soil movement and deposition occur in these dry Mediterranean environments
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33 (García-Ruiz, 2010; Baartman et al. 2012; Martínez-Mena et al. 2012). To avoid tillage
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35 effects on our litter decomposition experiment, and therefore to ensure that only soil
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37 erosion was responsible for litter decomposition, litterbags were collected in December
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39 2012, before tillage operations occurred in the study area, after the first rainfall events in
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41 late autumn and before the next green manure seeding.
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48 To assess the effect of the different phases of soil water erosion on the surface litter
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50 decomposition dynamics, the hillslope was divided into three areas according to erosion
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52 criteria and replicate (n=4) plots (3 m long \times 2 m wide) were located at each landform
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54 position: 1) eroding positions, at the upper slope position, in which soil deposition onto
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56 litter (or burial of litter) is non-significant but collision with soil particles may occur; 2)
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4 transport positions, at the middle slope position, where enhancement of flow velocity
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6 may increase and fragmentation of litter by soil abrasion may predominate; and 3)
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8 depositional positions, at the lower slope position, where litter fragmentation by soil
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10 abrasion may also be significant and soil deposition onto litter may facilitate soil-litter
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12 mixing and improve the environmental conditions for microbial activity.
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16 To avoid the effects on surface litter decomposition of both UV radiation (280-400 nm)
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18 and raindrop impact, important abiotic drivers of litter decomposition in arid and semiarid
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20 ecosystems (Austin and Vivanco, 2006; Whitford, 2002), the plots were covered with
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22 polycarbonate sheets (0.4 cm thick), which eliminate 90% of UV-A and UV-B (optically
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24 equivalent to Lexan XL-1, GE, Pittsfield, Massachusetts, USA). The polycarbonate filters
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26 (3 x 0.5 m) were placed 30 cm above the ground in a rectangular-frame design, supported
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28 by stakes to allow adequate ventilation, and perforations were made in the filters to allow
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30 water infiltration following precipitation.
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34 To assess erosion rates, sediment quality and the microbial biomass transported within
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36 sediments during the litterbag incubation period, sediment traps (0.3 m long) and erosion
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38 pins (1 x 1 m) were installed close to each plot (n=4). Sediments were collected after each
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40 erosion event. Erosion pins were measured after installation on 28th July 2010, and were
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42 re-measured every two weeks and after each erosion event. The precipitation depth,
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44 intensity and duration of each rainfall event were obtained from a recording rain gauge,
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46 connected to a data-logger installed in the experimental area.
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49 50 51 52 53 3. Soil and sediment sampling and analysis

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55 At the end of the incubation period, soil biochemical properties were determined at each
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57 landform position. Within each plot, two soil samples were collected at 0-2 cm depth,
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4 sealed in plastic bags and stored in a refrigerator (4 °C) until being processed for
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6 microbial biomass estimates and C and N analyses. Soil and sediment samples were air-
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8 dried and sieved through a 2-mm sieve. The C and N contents in the mineral soil and
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10 sediments (<2 mm) were measured with a N/C analyzer (Flash 1112 EA, Thermo-
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12 Finnigan, Bremen, Germany). The microbial C in the soil and sediments was measured
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14 by a respirometer (MicroTrack 4200- Sy Lab, Gomensoro, Madrid) and estimated by
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16 following the calculations of Anderson and Domsch (1978). All soil analyses were done
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18 in triplicate.
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24 4. Litter collection, initial litter traits and litterbag construction and deployment

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26 Plant material was collected on May 30th, at a site close to the olive grove, and oven-dried
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28 at 30 °C for 7 days until constant mass. Only recently-senescent leaves and stems were
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30 selected in order to reduce variability within the litter substrate. The oven-dry weight was
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32 determined for five samples per litter type after drying at 55 °C for 4 days. Subsamples
33
34 were ground and their C and N contents analysed in an elemental analyzer (Flash 1112
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36 EA, Thermo-Finnigan, Bremen, Germany). In addition, subsamples (0.2 g) were
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38 combusted in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 5 h to determine the initial ash content. Leaf
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40 litter macro- (P, K, Mg, Ca and S) and micro-nutrient (Fe, Zn and Mn) concentrations
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42 were also measured by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-
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44 OES, Thermo Elemental Iris Intrepid II XDL, Franklin, MA, USA) after microwave-
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46 assisted digestion with HNO₃:H₂O₂ (4:1, v:v).
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53 Each litter type (*A. sativa* or *V. sativa*) was mixed thoroughly before placing
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55 approximately 3 g of leaves and fine stems (± 0.01 g) - cut into pieces of ~5 cm - inside
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57 10 x 10 cm litterbags constructed of fibreglass mesh with 1.4 mm² openings. Twenty-four
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4 litterbags (12 per litter type) were placed randomly on the soil surface in each plot, on
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6 28th July 2010. A total of 288 litterbags were left (2 litter types x 3 positions x 4 plots x
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8 12 replicates) for 144 days during the summer-autumn season in the study site. Each
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10 litterbag was carried inside an individual envelope to quantify how much litter was lost
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12 from the bags during transport. Before collecting the litterbags from each plot on 19th
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14 December 2010, the soil cover (%) in each litterbag was estimated.
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17 18 19 5. Laboratory processing and analyses 20

21 The litterbag contents (litter and infiltrated/accumulated soil) were separated using a 1-
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23 mm-mesh sieve. Any material not derived from litter (seedlings, stones, soil fauna or
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25 fungi) was removed by hand and the litter was then brushed manually to remove adhering
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27 mineral soil from the leaves and stems. After drying for 4 days at 55 °C, the litter of each
28
29 litterbag was weighed to determine the change in mass. The soil within each litterbag was
30
31 also weighed. The litterbag contents were ground, and subsamples from each litterbag
32
33 were combusted in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 5 h to determine the ash content. In
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35 addition, the C and N contents of subsamples from each litterbag were determined in an
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37 elemental analyzer (Flash 1112 EA, Thermo-Finnigan, Bremen, Germany). All the data
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39 were expressed on an ash-free dry matter basis to exclude any mass gain resulting from
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41 the entry of mineral soil into the bags. However, because during litterbag incubation the
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43 litter gets mixed with a significant amount of mineral soil (the so called “soil-litter
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45 matrix”; Throop and Archer, 2007; Barnes et al. 2012; Hewins et al. 2012), an additional
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47 correction was performed according to the methods proposed by Harmon et al. (1999). To
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49 accomplish this, the ash-free dry mass was determined individually for a subsample of
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4 the soil infiltrated/deposited within each litterbag. Then, the ash-free dry mass of the
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6 decomposing material (litter) fraction of the bulk dry mass was calculated as follows:
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$$F_{\text{litter}} = m_{l+s} / m_l + m_s \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

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11 Where m is the ash-free dry mass and the subscripts $l+s$, l and s denote bulk (litter and
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13 soil), litter (as reference/decomposing material) and soil, respectively. Then, this
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15 correction factor was multiplied by the oven-dry sample weight (d) to obtain the mass of
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17 the remaining substrate (M):
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$$M = d \times F_{\text{litter}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

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23 After the ash correction, the ash-free dry mass remaining was calculated based on the
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25 assumption that the litter mass loss should follow a linear decay model. For the linear
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27 model, the ash-free dry mass remaining was fitted to the model $M_t / M_0 = -kt + a$, where
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29 M_t is the ash-free dry mass remaining at time t , M_0 is the ash-free dry initial mass, k is the
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31 litter-specific decay constant and a is a constant.
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36 According to previous studies (Throop and Archer, 2007; Barnes et al. 2012; Hewins et
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38 al. 2013), the percentage ash can be used as a conservative index of soil
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40 accumulation/infiltration and accounts only for the soil adhering to litter surfaces after
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42 sieving and brushing. However, there is a large proportion of soil that infiltrates litterbags
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44 and covers or mixes with litter without adhering to the litter surface. This occasional soil
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46 input and output through litterbags is mainly a consequence of water transport processes,
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48 which can be highly significant in our Mediterranean agroecosystems. Therefore, the
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50 weighed soil within each litterbag was also used as an index of the soil particles
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52 transported and redistributed within the hillslope by soil water erosion to assess the role
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54 of soil erosion in litter mass loss rates.
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4 6. Conceptual framework and description of the carbon balance approach
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7 In a previous study, soil C losses (at 0-5 cm depth) driven by the conversion from forest
8 to olive grove were estimated to be 674 g C m⁻² after 100 years of cultivation (Martínez-
9 Mena et al. 2008), of which approximately 75 % were attributed to soil water erosion (5 g
10 C m⁻² yr⁻¹).
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16 Previous to the green manure incorporation, a steady-state equilibrium can be assumed
17 with regard to the SOC level since this agricultural field has been under the same
18 management practice for at least 100 years (Burke et al. 1995; Lal, 2008). Therefore, we
19 assumed that C sequestration within the soil surface began after the first green manure
20 incorporation and continued until pre-cultivation SOC levels (e.g., those in the adjacent
21 open forest) were reached, and therefore a new equilibrium could be assumed.
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31 To assess the potential contribution of green manure incorporation to the annual rate of C
32 accumulation in our cultivated soil, we used the conservation mass approach proposed by
33 Yoo et al. (2005), whereby any change in the C stored in the soil per unit of time (Δt) is
34 given by the difference between C inputs (plant C inputs and depositional SOC inputs)
35 and losses from the soil (decomposition/mineralisation rates and erosional loss of SOC):
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$$43 \quad dS/dt = NPP - R_H - \varepsilon \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

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45 Where S is SOC storage (g C m⁻²), t is time, NPP is the annual plant biomass input
46 derived from green manure incorporation (g C m⁻² yr⁻¹), R_H is the proportion of
47 aboveground C biomass lost to the atmosphere through decomposition (g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) and
48 ε is the C mobilised by water erosion (g C m⁻² yr⁻¹).
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55 The annual aboveground biomass C derived from green manure (NPP) was assumed to be
56 similar to that in a nearby site over a four-year period (2010-2013) (49 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹;
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4 Martínez-Mena et al. 2013). The C decomposition constant (k_c , yr^{-1}) of green manure was
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6 determined for each land form position, pooling both litter types, by fitting the single
7
8 linear decay model $C_t/C_0 = -k_c t + a$, where C_t and C_0 are the ash-free C content of the
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10 litter at time t and time 0, k_c is the litter-specific C decay constant and a is a constant. The
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12 decay rate for the whole agricultural field was estimated as the average across the
13
14 landform positions and pooling both litter types. In order to compare the average litter
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16 decomposition rate within the agroecosystem to those of the net primary production
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18 derived from green manure and soil erosion, the decomposition of C had to be expressed
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20 on the same scale ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). To accomplish this, we assumed that all C derived from
21
22 the cover crop mean annual production ($49 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Martínez-Mena et al. 2013)
23
24 would eventually enter the litter pool and be decomposed at the average rate measured
25
26 across landform positions (k_c). Therefore, we obtained an estimate of the proportion of
27
28 aboveground biomass C lost through decomposition ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) by multiplying the
29
30 cover crop C input values by k_c (R_H in Eq. 3), and by difference the proportion of C
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32 incorporated into the soil. Soil erosion rates were estimated from erosion pin
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34 measurements across different landform positions along the hillslope. For more details,
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36 see section 2.2.

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46 In summary, data of soil C pools and losses caused by land-use change previously
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48 reported for this rainfed olive grove (Martínez-Mena et al. 2008) were combined with
49
50 new estimates of C gains and losses derived from green manure incorporation and erosion
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52 rates in order to assess the effect of green manure incorporation on the annual SOC
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54 accumulation rate of this rainfed olive grove (dS/dt in Eq.3) and therefore the potential of
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4 this cultivated soil for recovering previous SOC losses driven by land-use change, as a
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6 mitigation strategy.
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8 9 7. Statistical analyses

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11 Differences in the litter decay rates and C, N and ash contents at the end of the incubation
12
13 period were analysed with a two-way, split-plot model ANOVA in which position
14
15 (eroding, transport and deposition) and litter type (*Avena* and *Vicia*) were considered
16
17 main effects. Plot replicate was nested within position experimental units and was
18
19 considered a random factor. A t-test was performed to compare the initial nutrient
20
21 concentrations for each litter type. Soil and sediment properties were analysed with a
22
23 one-way split-plot model ANOVA, in which position was considered the main effect.
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25 Plot replicate was nested within position experimental units and was considered a random
26
27 factor. Differences in soil input into litterbags between positions were also analysed with
28
29 one-way ANOVA. Prior to analysis, data were natural-log transformed to meet ANOVA
30
31 assumptions. Across positions, linear regression analyses were performed separately for
32
33 each litter type, to evaluate the relationships between litter mass remaining and C and N
34
35 remaining, soil adhering to litter surfaces (ash content) and soil particles transported
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37 within the hillslope by soil water erosion (infiltrated/deposited soil within each litterbag,
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39 in grams). In addition, parameters related to litter quality (C and N content or C:N) or soil
40
41 water erosion were included in multiple linear regression models, and the stepwise
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43 procedure was used to assess their influence on mass loss patterns for each litter type and
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45 position separately. All analyses were performed using SPSS 15.0 (Chicago, IL, USA).
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58 **3. Results**

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4 3.1. Erosion/deposition patterns and soil characteristics along the hillslope
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6 During the experiment (from 28th July to 15th December 2010), 23 events produced a total
7 rainfall of 137 mm, of which only three rainfall events produced soil water erosion in the
8 experimental area. Two rainfall events of 20 and 45 mm, respectively, and moderate- to
9 high-intensity (maximum intensity in 30 min of 23 and 20, respectively), which occurred
10 during the same week in August 2010, accounted for 99 % of total soil loss in the
11 experimental area, leading to the burial of most of the litterbags located at the
12 depositional positions. According to our erosion pin measurements, total soil loss during
13 the study period was about 1800 and 1665 g soil m⁻² at the eroding and transport
14 positions, respectively, while 3147 g soil m⁻² was accumulated at the depositional
15 positions. Therefore, 91% of the eroded soil was deposited locally within the same
16 dynamic hillslope.
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33 Soil bulk density did not differ between landform positions (Table 1). Lower percentages
34 of the finest material (silt plus clay) and higher sand contents were observed at eroding
35 positions, in comparison to depositional positions. Interestingly, this particle size
36 distribution pattern was not consistent with the significantly higher soil total N content
37 (F=8.51; P=0.008) or the slightly higher (although not significantly so; F=0.58; P=0.577)
38 SOC content observed at eroding positions, relative to depositional positions. At transport
39 positions, the soil total N content was similar to that at depositional positions, while the
40 SOC content was comparable to that at eroding positions. As a result, higher but not
41 significantly different (P=0.139) C:N ratios were observed at transport positions with
42 respect to those at eroding and depositional positions. Soil microbial C ranged between
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4 1.28 and 1.41 g kg⁻¹ and did not differ along the hillslope, although slightly higher values
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6 were observed at transport positions.
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9 The C content in the sediments ranged from 11.1 to 13.5 g kg⁻¹ in the experimental site
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11 and there were no significant differences between landform positions (P=0.807).
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13 However, the total N contents in the sediments at transport positions were significantly
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15 lower than those at eroding and depositional positions (F=3.44; P=0.048; Table 1). In
16
17 regard to the C:N ratios in the sediments, there were no significant differences between
18
19 landform positions (P=0.463). The microbial C values in sediments were somewhat
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21 higher than those in soils (ranging from 1.47 to 1.82 mg kg⁻¹) and were higher, although
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23 not significantly so, at eroding and transport positions than at depositional positions
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25 (Table 1).
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31 The C enrichment ratio (ER_C) varied slightly along the hillslope, although no statistically
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33 significant differences were observed between positions (P=0.420; Table 1). Higher ER_C
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35 values were observed at depositional positions (1.54 ± 0.44), indicating higher enrichment
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37 in organic C relative to the experimental site soil, while ER_C values of 1.05 ± 0.44 and
38
39 1.11 ± 0.38 were found at transport and eroding positions, respectively. However, the ER_N
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41 ratios showed N impoverishment at depositional positions compared with eroding and
42
43 transport positions. The enrichment ratio for microbial C (ER_{MC}) diminished along the
44
45 hillslope (eroding > transport > deposition), although no statistically significant
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47 differences between landform positions were found.
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52 3.2. Litter mass loss

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55 At the end of the incubation experiment, significantly different decay rates were observed
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57 between landform positions, with the greatest ash-free litter mass losses occurring at
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4 depositional positions for both litter types ($F=203.65$; $P<0.0001$; Fig. 1A). Contrary to
5
6 expectations, the mass loss rates at eroding positions were slightly higher than those at
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8 transport positions. Across positions, vetch litter decomposed more rapidly than common
9
10 oat litter ($F=172.49$; $P<0.0001$). However, while vetch litter decomposed more than twice
11
12 as fast as common oat litter at eroding and transport positions, the difference in mass loss
13
14 between litter types diminished at depositional positions.
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18 The litter ash content had increased at the end of the incubation experiment for both litter
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20 types and was greater at depositional positions (Fig. 1B). This is consistent with the five-
21
22 fold higher value of infiltrated/accumulated soil and higher soil cover (%) for the
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24 litterbags at depositional positions, with respect to eroding and transport positions, at the
25
26 end of the decomposition experiment (Fig. 1C; Table 1). Indeed, the litter mass loss was
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28 directly related to the soil adhering to litter surfaces (% ash; Fig. 2b; R^2 values ranging
29
30 from 0.17 to 0.42 at $P<0.05$) and the soil particles transported within the hillslope by soil
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32 water erosion (infiltrated/deposited soil within each litterbag; Fig. 2c; R^2 values ranging
33
34 from 0.30 to 0.64 at $P<0.05$). These relationships were consistent across landform
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36 positions and litter types, being strongest at eroding and transport positions (Fig. 2).
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43 3. 3. Initial litter traits and changes in C and N during decomposition

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45 Analysis of the leaf-litter initial nutrient concentrations showed significantly higher
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47 contents of some macro- (B, Ca, K, Mg and S) and micro-nutrients (Fe) in *V. sativa* than
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49 in *A. sativa* litter (Table 2). The initial mean C percentages in common oat litter were
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51 significantly higher than those in vetch litter (Table 2; $F=79.81$, $P<0.0001$), while the
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53 initial N percentage in vetch litter was two-fold higher than that in common oat litter
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58 ($F=26.92$, $P=0.001$).
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4 There were tight linear relationships between the percentage of litter mass remaining and
5 the percentages of C mass remaining (Figures 3a, 3b) and N mass remaining (Figures 4a,
6 4b). Although the relationship between percentage of C mass remaining and percentage
7 of mass remaining was nearly 1:1, percentage of N mass remaining showed a clear
8 tendency to exceed the percentage of mass remaining for both litter types, especially at
9 transport positions. While the litter C content had decreased slightly at the end of the
10 decomposition experiment for both litter types across landform positions (Fig. 5A), the
11 smaller N loss relative to the total mass loss led to increases in litter N content at
12 transport positions for both litter types (Fig. 5B). The initial C:N ratios differed between
13 litter types (Table 2) and declined significantly with elapsed time across landform
14 positions (Fig. 5C).

31 3.4. Factors controlling mass loss rates

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33 Multiple regression analyses (stepwise) were performed for each litter type and landform
34 position in order to identify the factors controlling litter decomposition in this dry
35 Mediterranean agroecosystem. The models that best explained mass loss variations in the
36 different landform positions along the hillslope are shown in Table 3. At eroding and
37 transport positions, infiltrated/deposited soil within litterbags (as an index of soil
38 transport and deposition patterns caused by water erosion) was the main variable
39 explaining the rates of litter mass loss for both litter types (R^2 values ranged from 45 to
40 58 % depending on litter type and position; Table 3), and together with litter C content
41 accounted for 64-70 % of the variability in litter decay rates. However, at depositional
42 positions, where litterbags were often completely buried by soil, parameters more related
43 to litter quality (N content) were found to explain between 25 and 48 % of the variability
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4 in the mass loss rates of common oat and vetch, respectively, and together with soil
5 infiltrated/deposited into litterbags explained up to 32 and 68 % of the variability in the
6 litter decomposition rates of common oat and vetch, respectively. Across positions, the
7 infiltrated/deposited soil was the best predictor for both litter types, accounting for 63 and
8 43 % of the variability in the decomposition rates of common oat and vetch, respectively,
9 followed by different litter quality parameters depending on litter type.
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19 3.5. Implications of annual green manure incorporation for the soil carbon balance

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21 According to our values of annual aboveground biomass C ($49 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Martínez-
22 Mena et al. 2013) and the estimated average decay rate of green manure for the whole
23 agricultural field site ($k_c = 0.29 \text{ yr}^{-1}$), the annual C input derived from green manure was
24 estimated to be $35 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, while $14 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ were released to the atmosphere.
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26 This means that the annual C input into the soil derived from green manure incorporation
27 is five-times higher than the annual C loss driven by land-use change (i.e., conversion
28 from open forest to agricultural field) reported previously for this rainfed Mediterranean
29 olive grove ($\sim 7 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Martínez-Mena et al. 2008). This highlights the potential of
30 green manure incorporation for replacing previous soil C losses derived from land-use
31 change by enhancing the annual soil C sink capacity of this agroecosystem.
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45 Taking into account both lateral (soil erosion) and vertical (decomposition) C fluxes, the
46 annual C sink capacity of this hilly Mediterranean agroecosystem is $34 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (dS/dt
47 in Eq. 3). According to our estimates, soil C losses driven by the change in land use (674
48 g C m^{-2} ; Martínez-Mena et al. 2008) could be compensated after 20 years of annual green
49 manure incorporation in this rainfed olive grove.
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4. Discussion

The observed soil transport and deposition rates and associated loss of organic C due to water erosion during our study period were comparable to those found in a similar sloping agricultural field under temperate climate after an important erosion event (Van Hemelryck et al. 2011). The role of one single extreme rainfall event in accelerating soil C dynamics was evident in this study, in which a sharp increase in soil C mineralisation rates was observed immediately after an important erosion event occurred, and these were maintained for a few weeks before declining to lower basal rates. Despite the short-term nature of our experiment, our soil erosion rates were within the range of the annual erosion rates previously reported in longer-term studies conducted in similar dynamic hillslope Mediterranean environments (García-Ruiz, 2010; Taguas et al. 2010; Yoo et al. 2005). This highlights the important role of high-intensity rainfall events in the annual soil erosion rates in Mediterranean environments, where two or three rainfall events can be responsible for the main part of the annual soil erosion and associated C losses (Bartman et al. 2012; García-Ruiz, 2010; Martínez-Mena et al. 2008; Taguas et al. 2010). Likewise, the estimated litter decay rates derived from this experiment were comparable with those reported previously for cover crops in similar environments (Doneda et al. 2012; Gómez-Muñoz et al. 2014; Murungu et al. 2010) and our rates of erosion-induced C release to the atmosphere through decomposition along the hillslope ($9.5\text{-}23 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) were within the range of those estimated for a wide range of agricultural fields under different environmental conditions by Jacinthe and Lal (2001).

Our results show that soil erosion accelerated litter decomposition independently of litter quality, and that litter decay rates were controlled by different factors across landform

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4 positions in our agricultural field site (Fig. 2; Table 3). Both litter types decomposed
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6 faster at depositional positions than at eroding and transport positions, which is in
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8 agreement with our first hypothesis given the observed patterns of soil transport and
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10 redistribution along this dynamic hillslope during the study period (Fig. 1b). Our findings
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12 are consistent with previous studies which also found higher mineralisation rates at
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14 depositional positions (Van Hemelryck et al. 2011; Berhe, 2012). The fact that the mass
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16 loss rates of both litter types were tightly related to the soil infiltrated/deposited into the
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18 litterbags across landform positions (Fig. 2) highlights the role of soil water erosion in the
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20 enhancement of litter mass loss rates. However, contrary to our expectations and the
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22 findings of previous authors (Berhe, 2012; Pennock and Frick, 2001; Sariyildiz et al.
23
24 2005), we observed lower litter decomposition rates at transport than at eroding positions.
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26 This highlights the importance of the source of sediments with regard to their role as
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28 microbial and nutrient vectors (McCulley et al. 2004; Smith et al. 1994). In our
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30 agricultural field site, incoming sediments at eroding positions were transported from an
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32 adjacent undisturbed open forest with higher soil N and microbial C contents than the
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34 agricultural field (Almagro et al. 2013b), which explains the significantly higher N
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36 contents in the soil and sediments at eroding positions with respect to the transport
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38 positions (Table 1). This may have driven faster microbial litter colonisation, and hence
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40 somewhat-higher decomposition rates, at eroding than at mid-slope transport positions,
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42 where sediments were derived mainly from the agricultural field (Table 1).
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53 In any case, although soil transport and deposition played the largest role in the rates of
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55 litter mass loss along the hillslope, they could not account completely for the rapid litter
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57 decay observed at depositional positions. Indeed, while soil infiltration into litter was the
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4 main factor driving litter decomposition rates for both litter types at both eroding and
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6 transport positions, the litter N content played a larger role at depositional positions
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8 (Table 3). It is important to note that litterbags at depositional positions may have been
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10 colonised by greater pool of soil microorganisms a few days after deployment, when two
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12 important erosion events occurred in the experimental area and - as a consequence - most
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14 of the litterbags at depositional positions were buried. The occurrence of significant
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16 precipitation pulses together with high temperatures during the dry season may have
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18 stimulated microbial activity, while burial of litter may have facilitated soil-litter mixing
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20 and accelerated mass loss rates by extending the environmental conditions suitable for
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22 microbial decomposers during the warm-dry summer season (Throop and Archer, 2008;
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24 Barnes et al. 2012; Hewins et al. 2013; Lee et al. 2014). The fact that the litter N content
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26 was the main driver of the litter decomposition rates for both litter types at depositional
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28 positions suggests greater N demand by decomposer communities, which might have had
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30 limited access to exogenous N given the lower soil mineral N, the lower organic matter
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32 content in the soil-litter matrix within litterbags and the greater N impoverishment
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34 (according to the ER_N values) at these landform positions (Table 1).
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43 It is well known from several previous studies that substrate quality (nutrient content or
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45 C:N) plays a key role in litter decomposition dynamics (Aerts, 1997; Parton et al. 2007).
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47 In our study, the role of litter quality was evident, as vetch litter (more enriched in N and
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49 other essential nutrients; Table 2) decomposed more than twice as fast as oat litter across
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51 landform positions. However, erosional effects on litter decomposition dynamics (either
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53 through soil abrasion or facilitation of microbial decomposition) were also evident in our
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55 study. Therefore, as other authors have suggested (Throop and Archer, 2008; Hewins et
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4 al. 2013), the explicit incorporation of soil transport and deposition patterns into litter
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6 decomposition models should be considered in order to improve their ability to simulate
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8 decomposition patterns in arid, semiarid and Mediterranean ecosystems, where they tend
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10 to underpredict decomposition relative to field measurements, especially in arable lands,
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12 where increases in soil erosion rates are expected due to greater occurrence of extreme
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14 rainfall events as a result of future climate change.
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18 We have also demonstrated that the annual soil C sequestration capacity of this dry
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20 Mediterranean agroecosystem can be increased significantly by green manure
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22 incorporation into the system. According to our estimates, soil C losses arising from land-
23
24 use change could be compensated after a reasonable period (20 years) of green manure
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26 incorporation in this rainfed olive grove. Interestingly, our estimated annual SOC
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28 accumulation rates were comparable with those in a nearby agricultural field, under
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30 similar management and environmental conditions, in which an increase in the SOC stock
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32 (at 0-5 cm depth) of about 109 g C m^{-2} was observed after four years of green manure
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34 incorporation (i.e., $27 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Almagro et al. 2013a). It is important to note that
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36 these values could be even higher if we take into account a reduction in erosion due to
37
38 green manure incorporation. According to previous studies comparing soil erosion rates
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40 under different management practices (conventional vs reduced tillage and/or green
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42 manure; Almagro et al. 2013b; Alliaume et al. 2013; Gómez et al. 2009), soil erosion
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44 rates could be reduced by between 33 and 50 % with green manure incorporation. In any
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46 case, we acknowledge that our estimates should be taken with caution and interpreted as a
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48 proxy since, as has been stated previously (Powlson, 2011 and references therein), the
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50 annual rate of C sequestration in soils is much greater in the early years after a change in
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4 land use or management is implemented and then gradually decreases. Therefore, even
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6 though more than 20 years should be necessary before the full potential for soil C
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8 sequestration of this Mediterranean agroecosystem is reached, this period of time is
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10 reasonable in terms of recovering the starting values.
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14 In conclusion, the results of this study stress the importance of soil erosion in litter
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16 decomposition dynamics, and emphasise the need to incorporate the effect of the different
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18 phases of soil erosion in litter decomposition models in dry and disturbed ecosystems.
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20 This is a necessary step towards understanding the relative importance of soil erosion
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22 with respect to other controlling factors, as well as its implications for the SOC balance
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24 of hilly Mediterranean agricultural fields. Moreover, green manure incorporation can be
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26 an efficient tool to increase the SOC in Mediterranean agroecosystems, thereby
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28 recovering previous SOC losses driven by land-use change and tillage. This highlights the
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30 potential of this management practice as a mitigation strategy.
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Table 1. Biophysical properties (mean \pm standard error) in soil and sediments and erosion/accumulation rates at different positions along the hillslope.

Position	Eroding	Transport	Deposition
Soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	1.37 \pm 0.1	1.36 \pm 0.05	1.51 \pm 0.03
Soil MWD (mm)	1.43 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.47 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}	1.56 \pm 0.03 ^a
Soil Texture			
Clay + silt (%)	67.57 \pm 12 ^b	74.42 \pm 8.48 ^{ab}	79.52 \pm 7.37 ^a
Sand (%)	32.42 \pm 4.2 ^b	25.57 \pm 3.0 ^{ab}	20.47 \pm 1.84 ^a
Soil organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	10.72 \pm 0.86	10.52 \pm 0.90	8.72 \pm 0.63
Soil total N (g kg ⁻¹)	1.24 \pm 0.04 ^a	0.93 \pm 0.12 ^b	0.96 \pm 0.07 ^b
Soil C:N	8.64 \pm 0.65	11.31 \pm 0.63	9.08 \pm 0.63
Soil microbial carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	1.28 \pm 0.17	1.41 \pm 0.59	1.30 \pm 0.49
Sediments OC content (g kg ⁻¹)	11.95 \pm 3.03 ^a	11.15 \pm 2.84 ^a	13.49 \pm 2.84 ^a
Sediments N content (g kg ⁻¹)	0.88 \pm 0.17 ^a	0.79 \pm 0.16 ^b	0.90 \pm 0.16 ^a
Sediments C:N	15.29 \pm 4.44 ^a	21.28 \pm 4.15 ^a	14.45 \pm 4.15 ^a
Sediment microbial carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	1.82 \pm 0.34	1.70 \pm 0.67	1.47 \pm 0.36
ER_C	1.11 \pm 0.38	1.05 \pm 0.44	1.54 \pm 0.96
ER_N	0.93 \pm 0.24 ^a	0.91 \pm 0.63 ^a	0.70 \pm 0.28 ^b
ER_C:N	1.76	1.88	1.59
ER_MC	1.43 \pm 0.23	1.20 \pm 0.41	1.13 \pm 0.59
Soil erosion/accumulation rates (g m ⁻²)	- 1800	- 1665	3147
SOC erosion/accumulation rates (g C m ⁻²)	- 21.5	- 18.5	42.5
Soil cover in retrieved litterbags (%)	20.6 \pm 3.7 ^a	8.5 \pm 3.3 ^a	70.2 \pm 3.7 ^b
Organic Matter in soil-litter matrix (%)	9.02 \pm 0.25 ^a	7.43 \pm 0.22 ^b	7.81 \pm 0.25 ^b

Different letters (a-b) within the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between landform positions, according to Tukey's test.

Table 2. Initial characteristics of the leaf litter material used in the decomposition experiment.

Litter type	<i>Avena sativa</i>	<i>Vicia sativa</i>
Water content (%)	4.79 ± 0.15	4.53 ± 0.22
Ash content (%)	5.63 ± 0.24 ^b	8.55 ± 0.29 ^a
C	44.18 ± 0.33 ^a	42.53 ± 0.24 ^b
N	1.08 ± 0.19 ^b	2.14 ± 0.41 ^a
C:N	41.41 ± 6.02 ^a	20.38 ± 3.56 ^b
Al	0.10 ± 0.02	1.45 ± 0.02
B	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a
Ca	0.16 ± 0.00 ^b	1.54 ± 0.05 ^a
Fe	0.06 ± 0.01 ^b	0.10 ± 0.01 ^a
K	1.46 ± 0.10 ^b	2.17 ± 0.05 ^a
Mg	0.08 ± 0.00 ^b	0.16 ± 0.00 ^a
Mn	0.03 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^b
P	0.20 ± 0.00 ^a	0.14 ± 0.01 ^b
S	0.11 ± 0.00 ^b	0.14 ± 0.00 ^a
Zn	0.01 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.00

For each litter type, means ± standard deviations (n=5 replicates of each litter) are reported. Different letters (a-b) within the same row indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between litter types, according to Tukey's test.

Table 3. Relationship between the percentage of ash-free dry mass remaining and potential decomposition controls at different positions along the hillslope according to erosion criteria.

Landform Position	<i>Avena sativa</i>						<i>Vicia sativa</i>					
	Independent variables	Unstandardized partial regression coefficient	Standardized partial regression coefficient	R ² _{adj}	F	P	Independent variables	Unstandardized partial regression coefficient	Standardized partial regression coefficient	R ² _{adj}	F	P
Eroding	Intercept	-2.68 ± 0.47					Intercept	1.38 ± 0.94				
	Soil (g)	-0.10 ± 0.01	-0.737	0.58	55.86	< 0.001	Soil (g)	-0.20 ± 0.03	-0.637	0.56	50.80	< 0.001
	C (%)	0.48 ± 0.12	0.322	0.70	46.08	< 0.001	C (%)	0.79 ± 0.26	0.316	0.64	35.40	< 0.001
Transport	Intercept	0.58 ± 0.94					Intercept	-0.39 ± 0.84				
	Soil (g)	-0.05 ± 0.00	-0.589	0.52	51.02	< 0.001	Soil (g)	-0.10 ± 0.01	-0.539	0.45	38.28	< 0.001
	C (%)	1.05 ± 0.25	0.380	0.66	47.11	< 0.001	C (%)	1.28 ± 0.22	0.500	0.68	48.82	< 0.001
Deposition	Intercept	4.3 ± 0.27					Intercept	1.26 ± 1.00				
	N (%)	1.46 ± 0.42	0.453	0.25	14.81	< 0.001	N (%)	0.63 ± 0.27	0.325	0.48	36.69	< 0.001
	Soil (g)	-0.20 ± 0.08	-0.304	0.32	10.88	< 0.001	Soil (g)	-0.26 ± 0.04	-0.555	0.68	41.94	< 0.001
Across positions	Intercept	1.44 ± 1.17					Intercept	0.83 ± 0.60				
	Soil (g)	-0.17 ± 0.02	-0.498	0.43	97.34	< 0.001	Soil (g)	-0.21 ± 0.01	-0.606	0.63	216.44	< 0.001
	N (%)	0.56 ± 0.16	0.230	0.50	64.55	< 0.001	C (%)	1.20 ± 0.13	0.414	0.79	230.20	< 0.001

Notes: Linear regressions were calculated for each litter type and position separately, and also across positions (including data for all positions); only statistically significant regression parameters are shown. All variables included in the multiple stepwise regression analysis were previously ln-transformed: soil infiltrated/deposited into litterbags (as an index of soil erosion), litter C and N content, and C:N in litter.

Figure 1. A Average decay rate (k ; % mass loss day⁻¹) and standard errors (SE) for *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* leaf litter at different eroding positions along the hill-slope. Within positions, means with different lowercase superscript letter differ significantly between litter types ($P < 0.05$). Within each litter type, values with different uppercase superscript letter differ significantly between eroding positions ($P < 0.05$). **B** Normalized ash content ($\% \text{ ash}_{\text{final}} : \% \text{ ash}_{\text{initial}}$) and standard errors (SE) for *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* leaf litter at different eroding positions along the hill-slope. Within positions, means with different lowercase superscript letter differ significantly between litter types ($P < 0.05$). Within each litter type, values with different uppercase superscript letter differ significantly between eroding positions ($P < 0.05$). **C** Infiltrated/deposited soil into litterbags and standard errors (SE) for *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* leaf litter at different eroding positions along the hill-slope. Within positions, means with different lowercase superscript letter differ significantly between litter types ($P < 0.05$). Within each litter type, values with different uppercase superscript letter differ significantly between eroding positions ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Relationship between litter decay rates (% ash-free litter mass loss day⁻¹) and infiltrated/deposited soil within each litterbag (as an index of soil erosion patterns) for each litter type and landform position. Symbols/shades of gray represent position treatments.

Fig. 3. Relationship between percent ash-free litter mass remaining and percent ash-free C mass remaining. Symbols/shades of gray represent position treatments. In each figure, regression lines are dashed and the 1:1 line is solid.

Fig. 4. Relationship between percent ash-free litter mass remaining and percent ash-free N mass remaining. Symbols/shades of gray represent position treatments. In each figure, regression lines are dashed and the 1:1 line is solid.

Fig. 5. Normalized carbon content ($\% C_{\text{final}}: \% C_{\text{initial}}$) (a), nitrogen content ($\% N_{\text{final}}: \% N_{\text{initial}}$) (b), and C:N ($CN_{\text{final}}: CN_{\text{initial}}$) (c) and standard errors (SE) for *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* leaf litter at different eroding positions along the hill-slope. Within positions, means with different lowercase superscript letter differ significantly between litter types ($P < 0.05$). Within each litter type, values with different uppercase superscript letter differ significantly between eroding positions ($P < 0.05$).

Figure

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